

SEASONAL HYDROCHEMICAL VARIABILITY AND IMPLICATIONS FOR GROUNDWATER QUALITY NEAR AN OPEN DUMPSITE IN ENUGU URBAN, SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Groundwater constitutes a major source of domestic water supply in many developing regions; however, anthropogenic activities, such as open waste disposal, threaten its quality. This study evaluates the seasonal hydrochemical variability of groundwater around the open Ugwuaji dumpsite in Enugu, Southeastern Nigeria, focusing on physicochemical parameters and their implications for water quality. We collected groundwater samples from hand-dug wells within the dumpsite vicinity and a control well during the wet and dry seasons. Eleven physicochemical parameters—temperature, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total solids (TS), total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), chloride (Cl^-), total hardness (TH), dissolved oxygen (DO), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), and nitrate (NO_3^-) - were analyzed using standard laboratory procedures. The results revealed pronounced seasonal variations, with hand-dug wells showing significantly wider concentration ranges than the control well. Wet season samples recorded elevated mean values for TS, TSS, TDS, and chloride, attributed to enhance leachate infiltration, while dry season samples exhibited higher EC, TH, and nitrate due to evapoconcentration effects. Chloride concentrations exceeded permissible limits in several samples, whereas pH values indicated acidic conditions during the dry season. Coefficient of variation analysis revealed greater variability in the wet season, particularly for chloride and EC, whereas nitrate and TDS dominated the variability

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in the dry season. The findings demonstrate that seasonal hydrochemical processes and waste-derived contamination significantly influence groundwater quality around the open Ugwuaji dumpsite. This study highlights the vulnerability of shallow aquifers in dumpsite environments and underscores the need for continuous monitoring, improved waste management practices, and provision of safe alternative water sources.

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater remains an indispensable source of potable water globally, particularly in developing countries where access to treated municipal water is limited (Lapworth, 2017; Egbueri and Unigwe, 2020). In Nigeria, hand-dug wells and shallow aquifers are primary sources of domestic water for a significant proportion of the population, especially in peri-urban and rural communities. Despite its importance, rapid urbanization, population growth, and poor environmental management practices threaten groundwater quality (Kumar *et al.*, 2020; Majee, Ghosh and Filippelli, 2026). The indiscriminate disposal of solid waste in open dumpsites is one of the most significant contributors to groundwater contamination in urban environments (Zhang *et al.*, 2019; Nwatu, 2023). These dumpsites generate leachate, which is a complex wastewater formed when precipitation percolates through decomposing waste materials and contains high concentrations of organic and inorganic pollutants (Mor *et al.*, 2018; Boateng *et al.*, 2019; Nwatu, 2023). When leachate infiltrates the subsurface, it alters the groundwater's hydrochemical characteristics and may render it unsuitable for consumption (Majee *et al.*, 2026). Hydrogeological conditions and climatic variability, particularly seasonal changes, strongly influence the extent of groundwater contamination around dumpsites. The distinct wet and dry seasons play a critical role in controlling contaminant transport and concentration in tropical regions such as Southeastern Nigeria. Increased rainfall during the wet season enhances leachate generation and promotes the vertical and lateral migration of contaminants into aquifers. Conversely, the dry season is associated with reduced recharge, increased evaporation, and consequent concentration of dissolved constituents (Ukah *et al.*, 2019; Ocheri *et al.*, 2020). Hydrochemical studies have demonstrated that physicochemical parameters such as electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, chloride, and hardness are reliable indicators of groundwater contamination from anthropogenic sources (Akinbile and Yusoff, 2018; Tiwari *et al.*, 2017; Egbueri *et al.*, 2021). Elevated concentrations of these parameters often signify leachate intrusion and groundwater quality degradation. Seasonal fluctuations in these parameters provide insight into the dynamic processes governing groundwater systems (Majee *et al.*, 2026). Despite several studies on groundwater contamination in Nigeria, detailed, site-specific investigations that integrate seasonal analysis with comparative evaluation against control conditions are required. The Ugwuaji dumpsite in Enugu represents a typical example of an open waste disposal site with potential impacts on the surrounding groundwater resources (Nwatu, 2023; Nwatu *et al.*, 2025). Therefore, this study aims to assess the seasonal variability of physicochemical parameters in groundwater around the Ugwuaji dumpsite, compare hydrochemical characteristics between hand-dug wells and a control well, and evaluate the implications of observed variations for groundwater quality and public health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area: The study was conducted at the Ugwuaji dumpsite in Enugu State, Southeastern Nigeria (Figure 1). Situated between latitudes 6°26'49.51"N and 6°27'39.44"N of the Equator and longitudes 7°32'10.18"E and 7°33'20.05"E of the Greenwich Meridian within Enugu urban area of Enugu State, the dumpsite covers an approximate area of 18.44 Hectares (184, 400m²), and has been in operation for over 2 decades. To the south of the dumpsite is Ugwuaji town, to its west is Independence Layout, and to the east and northeast are Ogui-Nike

Inland Town and Thinkers Corner, respectively. The area lies within a tropical climatic zone characterized by two distinct seasons: the wet season (April - October) and the dry season (November - March). The annual rainfall is typically high, promoting significant groundwater recharge during the wet season. Geologically, the area is underlain by sedimentary formations that favor the development of shallow unconfined aquifers. These aquifers are highly vulnerable to contamination because of their proximity to the surface and limited natural filtration capacity.

Fig.1: Map of Nigeria showing Enugu State

Land use: Land use around this dumpsite consists of a heavily built-up fully developed northern and western part and a northeastern/southeastern part that is currently actively developing with many parcels of land showing ongoing development, some as close as 2-3 meters from the dumpsite. The northeastern and southeastern border of the dumpsite represents a new development phase due to the rapid urbanization rate in the study area (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Land use around the Ugwuaji dumpsite in Enugu, Enugu State

The Ogui-Inland Town in the northern and northwestern boundary of the dumpsite has witnessed one of the fastest urban developments in Enugu in the last 30 years. It is also fully built-up with various land use types, including residential, institutional, commercial, and religious. However, shallow hand-dug wells are very common in the area because of the complete absence of piped-borne water in this urban settlement. Further residential development around this dumpsite will increase the population that may be exposed to using groundwater to meet their domestic needs.

Sample size, sampling design, and collection: The sample size comprised 28 groundwater samples from 6 pre-existing hand-dug wells, and 1 control well in the dumpsite vicinity. Sampling was performed for a period of 4 consecutive seasons of 2 wet seasons and 2 dry seasons (i.e., 2 years). Figure 3 shows the sample map produced for this study. All 7 wells were purposively selected; the six 6 hand-dug wells from the dumpsite downgradient to assess the impact of solid waste disposal, and the control well from the dumpsite's upgradient away from the impact of solid waste disposal in the dumpsite. Table 1 is a listing of all 7 wells sampled in this study and their geographic coordinates.

Table 1: Geographic coordinates of the selected hand-dug and control wells

S/N	Designation of groundwater sampling points	Geographic coordinates of wells sampled by hand (Hand-dug sample and control wells)		
		Latitude (X)	Longitude (Y)	Elevation (Z)
1	S1	7°32'54.52"E	6°26'24.78"N	165 m
2	S2	7°33'00.87"E	6°26'33.02"N	163 m
3	S3	7°33'00.86"E	6°26'33.02"N	159 m
4	S4	7°33'12.08"E	6°26'41.11"N	156 m
5	S5	7°33'80.55"E	6°26'45.79"N	153 m
6	S6	7°33'17.10"E	6°26'45.48"N	146 m
7	Control	7°32'46.75"E	6°25'44.99"N	184 m

Source: Nwatu *et al.* (2026)

Fig. 3: Sample map for the study showing hand-dug wells (blue) and control well (green)

All 7 wells were sampled 4 times ($7 \times 4 = 28$), twice during the wet season and twice during the dry season to capture seasonal variability. Standard sampling procedures were followed to avoid contamination, and samples were appropriately preserved before laboratory analysis.

Laboratory Analysis: The following physicochemical parameters were analyzed: temperature, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total solids (TS), total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), Chloride (Cl^-), total hardness (TH), dissolved oxygen (DO), Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), and Nitrate (NO_3^-).

Analyses were conducted using standard methods as outlined in APHA (2017).

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics, including mean, range, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation, were computed from the seasonal physicochemical parameter values (Singh *et al.*, 2018). A comparative analysis was conducted between seasons, and the results were evaluated against NSDWQ (2015) drinking water standards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seasonal Hydrochemical Characteristics: Significant seasonal variations in groundwater quality were observed. Hand-dug wells exhibited wider ranges of physicochemical parameters than the control well, indicating a strong anthropogenic influence from the dumpsite. Table 2 shows the mean results for the groundwater sampled in the 2 wet seasons.

Table 2: 2-Wet season physico-chemical parameters concentration (range and mean values) in groundwater samples from hand-dug and control wells

Physico-chemical Parameter	Unit	Hand-dug well samples		Control well samples	
		Range of values Min- Max	Mean value	Range of the values Min-Max	Mean value
Temperature (Temp)	⁰ C	27-30	28.67	28-29	28.50
Acidity (pH)		3.83-9.40	6.53	7.22-7.33	7.28
EC (EC)	$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$	157.80-1240	498.17	732-979	855.50
Total solids (TS)	mg/l	380.00-980.00	619.33	448.00-500.00	474.00
Total suspended solids (TSS)	mg/l	250.00-565.00	406.42	288.00-320.00	304.00
Total dissolved solids (TDS)	mg/l	60.00-460.00	296.42	160.00-180.00	170.00
Chloride (Cl ⁻)	mg/l	15.89-1800.00	290.00	16.28-18.87	17.58
Total hardness (TH)	mg/l	86.24-625.00	343.80	580.00-658.00	619.00
Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	4.05-7.41	6.07	7.96-8.62	8.29
Suphate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	mg/l	128.99-162.26	146.41	180.40-233.22	206.81
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	mg/l	0.12-0.42	0.23	0.19-0.32	0.26

Source: Nwatu *et al.* (2026)

During the wet season, groundwater samples from hand-dug wells exhibited considerable variability in physicochemical characteristics, with generally wider ranges compared to the control well. The temperature values ranged from 27°C to 30°C (mean: 28.67°C) in the hand-dug wells and from 28°C to 29°C (mean: 28.50°C) in the control well. The pH values in the hand-dug wells showed a broad range (3.83–9.40; mean: 6.53), indicating slightly acidic conditions on average, while the control well remained near neutral (mean: 7.28). EC in hand-dug wells varied widely (157.80–1240 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$; mean: 498.17 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), reflecting heterogeneous ionic concentrations, whereas the control well showed a narrower range (mean: 855.50 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Similarly, total solids (TS), total suspended solids (TSS), and total dissolved solids (TDS) were higher and more variable in hand-dug wells, with mean values of 619.33 mg/L, 406.42 mg/L, and 296.42 mg/L, respectively, compared to 474.00 mg/L, 304.00 mg/L, and 170.00 mg/L in the control well. Chloride concentrations in hand-dug wells showed extreme variability (15.89–1800 mg/L; mean: 290.00 mg/L), significantly exceeding values in the control well (mean: 17.58 mg/L), indicating a strong anthropogenic influence. TH ranged widely in hand-dug wells (mean: 343.80 mg/L), while the control well recorded higher mean hardness (619.00 mg/L). Dissolved oxygen (DO) levels were lower in the hand-dug wells (mean: 6.07 mg/L) than in the control well (8.29 mg/L), suggesting reduced water quality. The sulfate and nitrate concentrations were though slightly higher in the control samples. Overall, wet season results indicate enhanced

leachate infiltration, leading to elevated solids, chloride, and general variability in groundwater quality within the vicinity of the dumpsite.

In summary, the wet season groundwater samples showed elevated concentrations of total solids, suspended solids, dissolved solids, and chloride. These increases are attributed to the increased leachate infiltration resulting from increased rainfall and percolation. Table 3 shows the mean results for groundwater sampled in the 2 dry seasons around the dumpsite.

Table 3: 2-dry season physico-chemical parameters concentration (range and mean values) in groundwater samples from hand-dug and control wells during the two dry seasons

Physico-chemical Parameter	Unit	Hand-dug well samples		Control well samples	
		Range of values Min-Max	Mean value	Range of values Min-Max	Mean value
Temperature (Temp)	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	28-31	29.33	28.00	28.00
Acidity (pH)		3.86-5.71	4.98	5.18-5.30	5.24
EC (EC)	$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$	43.00-303.00	149.96	45.90-50.40	48.15
Total solids (TS)	mg/l	246.00-540.00	381.62	425.00-460.00	442.50
Total suspended solids (TSS)	mg/l	180.00-360.00	285.29	325.00-380.00	352.50
Total dissolved solids (TDS)	mg/l	0.00-260	96.33	80.00-100.00	90.00
Chloride (Cl^{-})	mg/l	10.60-81.90	26.19	9.92-10.60	10.26
Total hardness (TH)	mg/l	98.06-706.10	417.60	124.64-166.00	145.32
Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	3.00-5.50	4.13	6.80-7.00	6.90
Suphate (SO_4^{2-})	mg/l	18.16-90.60	42.36	68.32-75.34	71.83
Nitrate (NO_3^{-})	mg/l	0.01-0.38	0.28	0.25-0.30	0.28

Source: Nwatu et al. (2026)

From the abovementioned dry season results, groundwater samples continued to exhibit notable variability, although overall concentrations reflected reduced dilution and increased evapotranspiration effects. The temperature in the hand-dug wells ranged from 28°C to 31°C (mean: 29.33°C), which was slightly higher than the constant value observed in the control well (28°C). The pH values in the hand-dug wells were consistently acidic (3.86–5.71; mean: 4.98), whereas the control well showed slightly higher but still mildly acidic values (mean: 5.24). EC in hand-dug wells ranged from 43.00–303.00 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (mean: 149.96 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), which was significantly higher than the narrow and lower range observed in the control well (mean: 48.15 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Total solids (TS) and total suspended solids (TSS) were lower in hand-dug wells than in the wet season but still showed substantial variability, with mean values of 381.62 and 285.29 mg/L , respectively. The control well samples had higher mean TS (442.50 mg/L) and TSS (352.50 mg/L) values. TDS in hand-dug wells ranged from 0 to 260 mg/L (mean: 96.33 mg/L), while control samples remained within a narrower range (mean: 90.00 mg/L). Chloride concentrations decreased significantly in the dry season but remained higher in hand-dug wells (mean: 26.19 mg/L) than in the control well (10.26 mg/L). TH showed increased mean values in hand-dug wells (417.60 mg/L), exceeding control well values (145.32 mg/L), indicating concentration effects. Dissolved oxygen (DO) remained lower in hand-dug wells (mean: 4.13 mg/L) relative to the control well (6.90 mg/L). The sulfate and nitrate concentrations were moderate, with nitrate showing similar mean values in both the hand-dug and control wells (0.28 mg/L). Overall, the results of the dry season reflect the concentration of dissolved constituents due to reduced recharge, with persistent evidence of contamination in hand-dug wells despite lower variability compared to the wet season.

The observed seasonal differences highlight the combined effects of leachate infiltration during the wet season and evapotranspiration during the dry season in controlling groundwater hydrochemistry in the study area.

Table 3 presents a comparison of mean seasonal (wet and dry) physicochemical parameters based on mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variance.

Table 3: Mean seasonal concentrations of physicochemical parameters in groundwater samples from hand-dug wells, standard deviation, and coefficient of variance (%)

Physico-chemical Parameter	Unit	Wet season values			Dry season values		
		Mean value	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variance (CV) %	Mean value	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of variance (CV) %
Temperature (Temp)	^o C	28.67	0.8876	3	28.50	0.8876	3
Acidity (pH)		6.53	1.7430	27	7.28	0.52	10.00
EC (EC)	$\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$	498.17	351.2618	71	855.50	75.1922	50.00
Total solids (TS)	mg/l	619.33	187.0753	30	474.00	87.4124	23.00
Total suspended solids (TSS)	mg/l	406.42	110.2538	27	304.00	55.182	19.00
Total dissolved solids (TDS)	mg/l	296.42	120.4503	41	170.00	88.6949	92.00
Chloride (Cl ⁻)	mg/l	290.00	507.7823	175	17.58	24.1817	92.00
Total hardness (TH)	mg/l	343.80	171.8994	50	619.00	217.7673	52.00
Dissolved oxygen	mg/l	6.07	1.1510	19	8.29	0.7899	19.00
Suphate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	mg/l	146.41	12.5020	9	206.81	25.5887	60.00
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	mg/l	0.23	0.0884	38	0.26	0.3094	110.00

Source: Nwatu *et al.* (2026)

Analysis of the mean seasonal physicochemical parameters in groundwater samples from hand-dug wells revealed clear distinctions between the hydrochemical characteristics of the wet and dry seasons. Higher mean values were recorded for temperature (28.67°C), chloride (290.00 mg/L), total solids (619.33 mg/L), total dissolved solids (296.42 mg/L), and total suspended solids (406.42 mg/L) during the wet season. These elevated values indicate increased leachate infiltration and enhanced mobilization during periods of high rainfall. In contrast, the dry season exhibited higher mean values for pH (7.28), electrical conductivity (855.50 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), total hardness (619.00 mg/L), dissolved oxygen (8.29 mg/L), sulfate (206.81 mg/L), and nitrate (0.26 mg/L), reflecting concentration effects associated with reduced dilution and groundwater recharge.

The degree of seasonal variability, as measured by the coefficient of variation (CV), further highlighted the influence of seasonal processes. Wet season samples showed greater variability in chloride (175%), electrical conductivity (71%), total solids (30%), pH (27%), and total suspended solids (27%), indicating strong fluctuations driven by leachate dynamics and rainfall intensity. Conversely, the dry season variability was more pronounced in nitrate (110%), total dissolved solids (92%), sulfate (60%), and total hardness (52%), suggesting the accumulation and concentration of dissolved constituents over time. Temperature (3%) and dissolved oxygen (19%) exhibited similar variability across both seasons, indicating relative stability. The ranking of variability among parameters showed that chloride and electrical conductivity dominated wet season fluctuations, while nitrate and dissolved solids were the most variable during the dry season. These patterns emphasize the groundwater system's dynamic hydrochemical responses to seasonal environmental controls (see Figure 4).

The comparative assessment also revealed that the hand-dug wells consistently exhibited wider ranges of physicochemical values than the control well, confirming the influence of dumpsite-related contamination. In terms of absolute mean values, the hand-dug wells recorded higher wet season concentrations for temperature, total solids, total suspended solids, total dissolved solids, and chloride, whereas the control well showed higher values for pH, electrical conductivity, total hardness, dissolved oxygen, sulfate, and nitrate. During the dry season, hand-dug wells maintained higher mean values for temperature, electrical conductivity, chloride, total dissolved solids, and total hardness, whereas the control well exhibited higher values for pH, total solids, total suspended solids, dissolved oxygen, sulfate, and nitrate.

Overall, a greater number of physicochemical parameters exhibited higher mean values during the dry season than during the wet season, whereas the wet season was characterized by higher variability. These findings underscore the combined influence of leachate infiltration during the rainy season and evapotranspiration during the dry season in controlling groundwater hydrochemistry in the study area.

Fig. 4: Degree of variation between dry and wet season physicochemical values

The above findings are in agreement with those of Bhalla *et al.* (2013), Agbozu, Oghama and Akinyemi (2015) and Eseyin *et al.* (2018). The observed mean wet season groundwater (from hand-dug well samples) pH of 6.53 (neutral to weakly acidic) conforms with a dumpsite age of ≤ 20 years as observed by other researchers, such as Kundiri *et al.* (2017), Alawode *et al.* (2019), and Gomez *et al.* (2019). The higher mean wet pH observed in groundwater samples from hand-dug wells is due to the higher mobility and migration of dumpsite wastewater, which contaminates groundwater resources. Moreover, Ofomola *et al.* (2017) noted that decreased pH is consistent with lower heavy metal concentrations because of the reduction in heavy metal mobility (Li, *et al.*, 2018; Subba Rao, 2017). This is in agreement with our findings.

Comparison with Drinking Water Standards: A comparison of the mean seasonal physicochemical parameters with the limits of the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) reveals varying degrees of compliance and exceedance across parameters and seasons (Figure 5). Temperature values were slightly higher in the dry season (29.33°C) than in the wet season (28.67°C). Although both exceeded the NSDWQ reference value, they remained within the ambient environmental range and were not considered critical. The mean pH values for both seasons (6.53 and 4.98 in the wet season and 4.98 in the dry season) were below the acceptable NSDWQ limit of 6.5–8.5, indicating acidic conditions, particularly during the dry season. Dissolved oxygen (DO) showed seasonal contrast, with the wet season mean (6.07 mg/L) exceeding the minimum recommended

limit (5.0 mg/L), while the dry season mean (4.12 mg/L) fell below it, suggesting reduced water quality during the dry period. Nitrate concentrations remained well below the permissible limit of 50 mg/L in both seasons, with only a slight increase observed in the dry season (0.28 mg/L) compared to the wet season (0.23 mg/L), indicating minimal risk from nitrate contamination. EC values were higher in the wet season (498.17 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) than in the dry season (149.96 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), but both remained within the acceptable limit of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The total solids (TS) and total suspended solids (TSS) showed significant deviations from the standards. While the dry season mean TS concentration (381.62 mg/L) was within acceptable limits, the wet season mean TS concentration (619.33 mg/L) exceeded the recommended threshold. Similarly, the TSS values in both seasons (406.42 mg/L in the wet season and 285.29 mg/L in the dry season) far exceeded the NSDWQ limit of 50 mg/L, indicating substantial particulate contamination. The TDS values were higher in the wet season (296.42 mg/L) than in the dry season (96.33 mg/L), but both remained within the permissible limit of 500 mg/L. Chloride concentrations exhibited a marked seasonal difference, with the wet season mean (290.00 mg/L) exceeding the allowable limit of 250 mg/L, while the dry season value (26.19 mg/L) remained within acceptable bounds, reflecting strong wet season contamination influence. TH exceeded the NSDWQ limit (150 mg/L) in both seasons, with higher values recorded in the dry season (417.60 mg/L) than in the wet season (343.80 mg/L), indicating persistently hard water conditions. Sulfate concentrations followed a similar seasonal trend, with the wet season mean (146.41 mg/L) exceeding the permissible limit (100 mg/L), while the dry season mean (42.36 mg/L) remained within acceptable levels.

Fig. 5: Comparison of mean seasonal physicochemical values with NSDWQ permissible limits

Overall, parameters such as total hardness, total suspended solids, and chloride (in the wet season) consistently exceeded the NSDWQ limits, indicating a compromised groundwater quality. In contrast, nitrate, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, and temperature were generally within acceptable limits. Seasonal patterns further reveal that most physicochemical parameters (TDS, sulfate, pH, DO, chloride, EC, TS, and TSS) exhibited higher concentrations during the wet season, underscoring the role of leachate infiltration in contaminant transport. These findings are consistent with those of previous studies (Eseyin *et al.*, 2018; Alagbe *et al.*, 2019; Abba, 2026), which reported elevated physicochemical contamination during the wet season due to increased leachate mobility and infiltration.

Variability Analysis: This study's assessment of variability in physicochemical parameters provides critical insight into the dynamic behavior of groundwater systems influenced by anthropogenic activities. The CV revealed pronounced seasonal differences in the dispersion of physicochemical parameters in groundwater from hand-dug wells around the Ugwuaji dumpsite. Overall, the wet season exhibited greater variability than the dry season, indicating stronger fluctuations in groundwater chemistry during periods of intense rainfall. This heightened variability is particularly evident in chloride and electrical conductivity parameters, which showed significantly elevated CV values. The wide dispersion observed during the wet season reflects the episodic and uneven infiltration of leachate into the subsurface, driven by rainfall intensity, surface runoff, and heterogeneous waste composition. Such conditions promote irregular pulses of dissolved ions and suspended materials into the groundwater system, resulting in water quality temporal inconsistencies. Conversely, the dry season was characterized by relatively lower variability for most parameters, although notable exceptions were observed for nitrate and total dissolved solids, which exhibited high CV values. This pattern reveals that while overall fluctuations are reduced in the absence of rainfall, certain dissolved constituents become increasingly concentrated due to reduced dilution, localized accumulation, and prolonged residence time within the aquifer. The ranking of variability further highlights distinct seasonal controls on groundwater chemistry. During the wet season, the parameters associated with leachate influence, particularly chloride and electrical conductivity, dominated the variability patterns. Variability was more strongly associated with dissolved constituents, such as nitrate and total dissolved solids, in the dry season, reflecting concentration processes. Temperature and dissolved oxygen exhibited relatively low and stable variability across both seasons, indicating that these parameters are less sensitive to seasonal contamination dynamics. The consistently higher variability observed in hand-dug wells compared to the control well underscores the dumpsite's influence as a point source of contamination. The control well, which is characterized by narrower parameter ranges and lower variability, reflects more stable hydrochemical conditions with minimal anthropogenic disturbance. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that the groundwater in the study area is subject to significant seasonal heterogeneity, driven largely by dumpsite-related activities.

Conceptual Framework for Hydrochemical Processes: A combination of natural processes and anthropogenic influences controls the hydrochemical characteristics observed in this study, with seasonal variations playing a central role in determining groundwater quality. Two dominant hydrochemical processes; leachate infiltration during the wet season, and evapotranspiration during the dry season were identified as the primary drivers of groundwater chemistry in the study area. These are well illustrated in the conceptual framework shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Conceptual framework developed for the study

During the wet season, increased precipitation enhances leachate generation and mobilization from the dumpsite. Rainwater percolates by decomposing waste materials, dissolving soluble constituents, and transporting them downward into the subsurface. This process leads to elevated concentrations of total solids, suspended solids, dissolved solids, and chloride in groundwater. The high variability observed in these parameters further reflects the irregular nature of leachate migration, which is influenced by factors such as soil permeability, waste composition, and rainfall intensity. The leachate influx also contributes to changes in pH and dissolved oxygen levels, indicating active biochemical processes within the aquifer. In contrast, the dry season experiences reduced groundwater recharge and increased evaporation, resulting in dissolved ion concentration within the aquifer system. Under these conditions, parameters such as electrical conductivity, total hardness, and nitrate exhibit higher mean values, indicating increased ionic strength and reduced dilution capacity. The accumulation of dissolved constituents is further enhanced by longer residence times and limited aquifer flushing, allowing solutes to persist and concentrate over time. The interplay between these two processes creates a dynamic hydrochemical environment in which the groundwater quality fluctuates seasonally. While the wet season facilitates contaminant transport and dispersion, the dry season promotes dissolved substances' concentration and persistence. This dual mechanism highlights the vulnerability of shallow aquifers in dumpsite environments, where both infiltration and accumulation processes contribute to the deterioration of water quality.

Environmental and Public Health Implications: The observed hydrochemical conditions have significant implications for environmental quality and public health, particularly in communities reliant on untreated groundwater from hand-dug wells. The presence of elevated concentrations of key physicochemical parameters indicates a compromised groundwater system with potential risks for human consumption (Adimalla, 2020; Majee *et al.*, 2026). The acidic conditions observed in several samples, especially during the dry season, are of particular concern because low pH enhances the mobility and solubility of heavy metals in groundwater. This

increases the likelihood of toxic metal contamination, even when such metals are not directly measured in this phase of the study (Nwatu *et al.*, 2025; Majee *et al.*, 2026). Elevated chloride concentrations, particularly during the wet season, serve as strong indicators of anthropogenic pollution and may affect water taste, corrosivity, and overall acceptability for domestic use. High levels of total suspended solids and total solids indicate particulate and dissolved contaminants, which can harbor pathogens and reduce water clarity. The exceedance of total hardness limits may result in potential scaling issues in domestic water systems and may also affect water palatability. Additionally, reduced dissolved oxygen levels observed in some samples indicate poor water quality and possible organic pollution (Majee *et al.*, 2026). The seasonal nature of these variations introduces an additional dimension of risk because groundwater quality is not constant throughout the year. Users may unknowingly consume water that is relatively safe during one season but significantly contaminated during another, particularly during the wet season when leachate infiltration is most pronounced. The findings highlight the broader environmental impact of improper waste disposal practices on groundwater resources. The contamination of shallow aquifers not only affects human health but also threatens the sustainability of local water supplies (Nwatu *et al.*, 2025; Majee *et al.*, 2026). Without adequate intervention, continued exposure to contaminated groundwater may result in long-term health consequences, including gastrointestinal disorders and potential heavy metal toxicity. These observations underscore the urgent need for improved waste management practices, regular groundwater monitoring, and safe alternative water sources to protect public health in the study area.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that seasonal hydrochemical variability and anthropogenic contamination significantly influence groundwater quality in the vicinity of the Ugwuaji dumpsite. The analysis of physicochemical parameters revealed clear spatial differences between the hand-dug wells and the control well, as well as pronounced temporal (seasonal) variations driven by climatic conditions. Increased leachate infiltration characterized wet season conditions, resulting in elevated concentrations of solids and chloride, alongside greater variability in groundwater chemistry. In contrast, the dry season promoted the concentration of dissolved constituents due to reduced recharge and evapotranspiration processes, resulting in higher values of electrical conductivity, total hardness, and related parameters. These seasonal dynamics underscore the dual role of rainfall in mobilizing contaminants and dry conditions in concentrating them within the aquifer. Comparison with drinking water standards indicates that several key parameters, including total hardness, total suspended solids, and chloride, exceed permissible limits under certain conditions, while pH values reflect persistent acidity. These deviations indicate deterioration of groundwater quality and raise concerns about its suitability for domestic use without treatment. Overall, the findings highlight the vulnerability of shallow groundwater systems in dumpsite environments and emphasize the need for proactive management to safeguard water quality and public health.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A combination of monitoring, management, and policy interventions is required to mitigate the observed groundwater quality deterioration and associated risks. Regular and systematic groundwater quality monitoring should be established to track seasonal variations and detect early signs of contamination. Such monitoring should be expanded to include microbiological and heavy metal assessments to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of water safety. Transitioning from open dumping practices to engineered waste management systems that incorporate leachate collection and containment mechanisms is urgent. This will significantly reduce the infiltration of contaminants into the underlying aquifers. In the interim, protective measures such as waste disposal site lining and improved drainage systems should be implemented to minimize leachate migration. Communities relying on hand-dug wells should be provided with safe and treated water sources, particularly during periods of heightened contamination risk. Public awareness programs are also essential to

educate residents on the potential health implications of consuming untreated groundwater and to promote safe water handling practices. Finally, land-use planning and regulatory enforcement should restrict the siting of water supply sources in close proximity to waste disposal sites. Integrated environmental management strategies that combine hydrogeological assessment with waste management planning are essential for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the study area's groundwater resources.

DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval: This study did not involve human participants or animal experimentation; therefore, formal ethical approval was not required. All procedures involving data handling and analysis were conducted in accordance with standard academic and institutional guidelines.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The authors hereby declare that no generative artificial intelligence (AI) technologies such as large language models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, XLNet, Ernie 3.0 Titan, etc.) and text-to-image generators were used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

Declaration of Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no known conflicts of interest or personal relationships that have influenced the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of Data Availability: Data are available upon request from the corresponding author.

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